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Voxidov Dilshod Odilovich*Namangan davlat universitetining tayanch doktoranti,
+998972120387, geograf-namdu@mail.ru.***MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA AN'ANAVIY
TA'LIMIY O'YINLAR NAZARIYASI VA METODIKASI**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10600635>

Annotatsiya: Maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalaridagi tarbiyalanuvchilar biliminin yanada rivojlantirish, an'anaviy ta'limiy o'yinlarning nazariy asoslariga qaratilgan bilim va ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning metodologik asoslariga qaratilgan bo'lib, ta'limiy o'yinlarning metodologik xususiyatlari, o'yinlarning metodologik bosqishlariga qaratilgan tushunchalarning pedagogik jihatlari yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'limiy oyinlar nazariyasi, metodologiya, tayyorlov guruhlari, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari, oyinlar bosqichlari, tarbiyalanuvchilar

Introduction

Today, realizing the intellectual potential of young people and bringing them to adulthood as well-rounded individuals has become a priority direction of our state's policy in raising a mature generation. Because only physically healthy and spiritually mature individuals can create a great future.

In order to further improve the system of preschool education in our country, to strengthen the material and technical base, to expand the network of preschool educational institutions, to provide qualified pedagogic personnel, to radically improve the level of preparation of children for school education, to modernize the educational process, to implement educational programs and technologies, to create conditions for all-round intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of children a number of decisions, laws and by-laws such as PQ-2707 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, December 29, 2016, "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017 - 2021" and PQ - 3261 on September 9, 2017, "On measures to fundamentally improve the preschool education system", PQ - 3955 on September 30, 2018, "Measures to improve the management of the preschool education system" were created.

Also, in the "Educational program for stu-

dents" of the UNICEF organization, it was noted that the use of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process of primary schools is an urgent issue.

Literature review

Y.Y.Voronova, V.P.Kustova, N.S.Anisomova, M.Ryabsev, N.I.Taylakov and others conducted research on the use of multimedia technology at various stages of education. Also, scientists such as A.A.Abdukadirov, M.M.Aripov, T.R.Azlarov, A.I.Ashirova, U.Sh.Begimkulov, T.F.Bekmurodov, R.R.Boqiyev, F.M.Zakirova, H.Z.Ikromova, M.E.Mamarajabov, B.B.Mominov, K.A.Torakulov, U.Y.Yuldashev, A.G.Hayitov, S.S.Ghulomov studied various problems of using computers in education.

Nature and its protection, based on traditional methods, in preparatory groups was focused in methodical works of O.Boltaboyeva, N.Alimov, N.Bikbayeva, N.Umarova, M.Khalilova and other pedagogues-scientists on environmental education.

Methods of research

Scientific-theoretical analysis, historical-comparative analysis and generalization methods were used during the research.

Analysis and results

Due to the fact that the use of educational games and distance learning technologies occupy a special place in the education system, including the educational

process of preschool educational institutions, it was aimed to study these issues more widely.

Educational games: tasks, features and main types. Educational games occupy an important place in the modern psychological and pedagogical technology of education. Conducting educational games as a method became widespread in the 70s of the 20th century. Currently, there are various types of educational games according to the field of application. For example, in the training of officers, there are military games, plot-role games for actors, and special training for businessmen and leaders. It should be noted that educational games do not use only a simple game style. In the course of the game, you can use group, joint discussion, conducting tests and surveys, and creating role-playing situations. In other words, it gives the opportunity to carry out and use questionnaires, sociometry, "brainstorming" and other methods in a limited amount. At the same time, the game style has some special features in pedagogy. In the process of education, the game is used as an auxiliary element, partially as an addition to the theoretical material, and it cannot be the main method [1].

In pedagogy, they create an opportunity to activate the educational process and create creativity of students. Psychological trainings using game methods increase the interest of students in search of ways to solve problems encountered in life, as well as create an environment of open attitude. Developmental game, as an activity, ensures the development of a child's age-dependent type of movement, a similar way of thinking, the transition to visual-form thinking, and the formation of verbal thinking in the form of a concept. Therefore, the student's learning of various traditional games creates the necessary basis for mastering computer games [2].

A rich experience in using the computer as an educational tool has been gathered in the USA, France and Great Britain. In the

United States, a number of models of teaching children using computers at home and at school have been developed. Studies have shown that children in computer-trained groups have significantly higher results than children in non-computer-trained groups.

The program "Children and popular culture" operated in the USA. An important conclusion obtained as a result of the activity of this program is that the importance of games, including computer games, in the acquisition of knowledge is great. The authors emphasized the need to introduce computer technology into the practice of kindergartens. "National Association for the Education of Young Children - NAEYC" (Washington) developed the principles of using information technologies to ensure the development and education of young children [4].

Introduction of computer programs to the activities of children of preschool educational institutions, choosing the right software product and using them correctly, turns the computer game into a real tool in the play activities of children. Only then will the child's playing environment be sufficiently formed, and the computer will become a powerful factor in the development of the child's psyche and intellect [3].

Currently, there are a number of problems related to the organization of children's games and the enrichment of toys with new technologies, the introduction of computer development programs into preschool educational institutions.

Conclusion

The main tasks of educators of pre-school educational institutions are to further develop children's talents and abilities, to develop their educational prospects. It is known that the main goal of preschool education is to form a child's personality in a healthy and mature way, prepared for studying at school.

In order to achieve this goal, it is necessary to introduce information and communication technologies to the educational

process in preschool educational institutions, based on the fact that the current age is the information age. Accordingly, if the educator uses various pedagogical programs, electronic manuals, and pedagogical games in the training sessions, the barrier between the educator and the student will disappear, and the children's character will open up more widely. Children's observation and memory focus increase because there is no mandatory teaching of knowledge in training, positive results are achieved by voluntary acceptance of knowledge. The use of pedagogical and information technologies in preschool education is considered one of the urgent problems of the day. Observations show that 80-90 percent of students are highly interested in computer games. One of the urgent issues of today is to form preschool children's worldview and moral culture by showing them games, activities, color draw-

ings at different stages depending on their interests.

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Вохидов Дилшод Одилович

Докторант (PhD) Наманганского государственного университета
+998972120387, geograf-namdu@mail.ru

ТЕОРИЯ И МЕТОДИКА ТРАДИЦИОННЫХ РАЗВИВАЮЩИХ ИГР В ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются методические основы дальнейшего развития знаний учащихся дошкольных образовательных учреждений, формирование знаний и умений, ориентированных на теоретические основы традиционных образовательных игр и методические особенности образовательных игр, педагогические аспекты концепций, направленных на Также освещены методические подходы игр.

Ключевые слова: Теория развивающих игр, методика, учебные группы, дошкольные образовательные учреждения, этапы игр, обучающиеся.

Vokhidov Dilshod Odilovich

PhD student of Namangan State University
+998972120387, geograf-namdu@mail.ru

THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF TRADITIONAL EDUCATIONAL GAMES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Annotation: The article focuses on the methodological foundations of further development of the knowledge of students in preschool educational institutions, the formation of knowledge and skills focused on the theoretical foundations of traditional educational games and methodological features of educational games, pedagogical aspects of the concepts aimed at methodological approaches of games are highlighted as well.

Key words: Theory of educational games, methodology, training groups, preschool educational institutions, stages of games, students